

Reversible Gates for Programmable Photonics

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Abstract— We present and develop a formalism for the implementation of complex programmable photonic circuits taking as basic building blocks 2x2 reversible gates corresponding to rotation operations. These gates isomorphically correspond to well-known photonic components.

Keywords— programmable photonics, reversible gates, Introduction

In digital electronics it is customary to employ elementary irreversible gates for bit processing using boolean logic [1]. These gates are characterized by the fact that the number of input ports (or FAN-IN) is 2 while the number of output ports of FAN-OUT is 1. Figure 1 (a), (b) shows some basic examples of these gates, which are characterized by their so-called truth tables. The term irreversible reflects the fact that the input cannot be deduced from the output unambiguously. By cascading thousands of these gates one can build extremely complex combinatorial and sequential boolean circuits.

Fig. 1. Examples of irreversible AND (a) and XOR (b) gates and of a reversible SWAP gate (after [1])

Reversible gates on the contrary have the same number of input and output ports and are characterized as well by truth tables [1], [2]. For example figure 1(c) shows the example of a SWAP or Pauli-X gate. However, in this case, the input state can be deduced from the gate output as the gate operation can also be described by a unitary matrix transformation U . If \mathbf{I} and \mathbf{O} denote respectively the input and output vectors, the $\mathbf{O} = U\mathbf{I}$, hence $\mathbf{I} = U^{-1}\mathbf{O}$, but since U is unitary its inverse is given by the hermitian conjugate. Reversible gates can be employed to perform digital Boolean operations but this process is inefficient compared to the use of irreversible gates as it entails the use of fixed or *ancilla* bits and produces as well *garbage* bits, which are not useful to the rest of the computation. As a consequence, reversible gates are not employed in digital electronics.

Reversible gates have found however an application niche in the field of quantum computation [2]-[4]. The two main reasons are firstly that quantum computation does not rely on in Boolean logic but rather on the use of linear unitary

transformations. This is due to the fact that a qubit resembles more an analog than a digital signal as the multiplying coefficients α and β of the $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$ states can be continuously changed between 0 and 1. Indeed, the qubit processing by the logic gate is really carried altering its wave-like and not its particle-like properties. The second reason and equally important is that reversible gates can be engineered to exploit the garbage bits as heralding ports [3] to certify the correct operation of the gate.

Integrated photonic circuits for classical signal processing applications handle analog signals [5]-[7] and therefore it makes sense to consider the use of reversible gates as a basic building block to implement complex circuit structures. Here we develop the formalism for the implementation of complex programmable photonic circuits taking as basic building blocks a special family of 2x2 reversible gates (known as rotation gates). We first illustrate how these gates isomorphically correspond to well known photonic components such as directional and 3dB tunable couplers and push-pull phase shifters. We then show how these can be concatenated in two compact forms to implement tunable arbitrary 2x2 unitary transformers. These unitaries can be, in turn, assembled into two-dimensional configurations to feature field programmable gate arrays [8].

I. 2X2 ROTATION MATRICES

We consider the basic 2x2 Pauli matrices given by [1]:

$$\sigma_0 = I = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}; \quad \sigma_1 = X = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (1)$$

$$\sigma_2 = Y = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -i \\ i & 0 \end{pmatrix}; \quad \sigma_3 = Z = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}$$

The rotation matrices (by an angle θ) around axes x, y and z are given by:

$$R_x(\theta) = e^{-i\frac{\theta}{2}X}; \quad R_y(\theta) = e^{-i\frac{\theta}{2}Y}; \quad R_z(\theta) = e^{-i\frac{\theta}{2}Z} \quad (2)$$

It can be shown that:

$$R_x(\theta) = \begin{pmatrix} \cos(\theta/2) & i\sin(\theta/2) \\ i\sin(\theta/2) & \cos(\theta/2) \end{pmatrix} \quad (3)$$

$$R_y(\theta) = \begin{pmatrix} \cos(\theta/2) & -\sin(\theta/2) \\ \sin(\theta/2) & \cos(\theta/2) \end{pmatrix}$$

$$R_z(\theta) = \begin{pmatrix} e^{-i(\theta/2)} & 0 \\ 0 & e^{-i(\theta/2)} \end{pmatrix}$$

These rotations can be implemented in the photonics domain respectively by a tunable directional coupler (TDC), a 3 dB Mach-Zehnder tunable coupler (3dB-MZI) and two parallel waveguides including two phase shifters configured in push-pull mode as shown in figure 2(a) [5].

Fig. 2. (a) Isomorphism between 2x2 rotation operators and integrated waveguide components. (b) two alternatives for the implementation of arbitrary programmable 2x2 unitary transformers. (c) a reduced version of the configurations shown in (b) where one phase shifting stage has been suppressed.

By virtue of the Euler theorem [2] any arbitrary 2x2 unitary matrix U can be expressed in either of the two following sequential rotation matrix concatenation forms:

$$\begin{aligned} U &= e^{i\delta} R_z(\alpha) R_y(\beta) R_z(\gamma) \\ U &= e^{i\delta} R_z(\alpha) R_x(\beta) R_z(\gamma) \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Where α, β, γ and δ are a set of four real numbers. This means that compact configurations of a preceding and succeeding differential phase shifting units enclosing either a TDC or a 3-dB-MZI unit as shown in figure 2(b) can be employed to implement these arbitrary units.

To construct two-dimensional programmable arrays we consider a reduced version of the above configurations, which we term as gates:

$$\begin{aligned} G &= e^{i\delta} R_y(\beta) R_z(\gamma) \\ G &= e^{i\delta} R_x(\beta) R_z(\gamma) \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Here one of the phase shifting units is not included (in this case the one succeeding the tunable coupler) as shown in figure 2(c).

II. PROGRAMMABLE ARRAYS

Programmable arrays can be constructed by means of two dimensional assemblies of 2x2 gates given by (5). This is shown in Figure 3(a). Note as shown in figure 3(b) that since for every 2x2 G unit its input phase shifter (shown in blue) can be programmed to incorporate the effect of the required preceding phase shift as well as the fictitious succeeding phase shifter of the preceding 2x2 G unit then this configuration is actually equivalent to that of an array of arbitrary 2x2 unitary transformers. This structure can then be programmed to implement any arbitrary NxN unitary transformation as it has been shown in [5]. Furthermore, because of the reversible nature of the gates, both feedforward

and backward operations are possible, even simultaneously. This enables the possibility of implementing resonant and cavity structures with this field programmable reversible gate array configuration.

Fig. 3. (a) Two dimensional array arrangement of reversible G gates. (b) Detailed explanation of how the concatenation of a given Gate G_{ij} actually results in the possibility of implementing a unitary arbitrary transformation by the ij element.

III. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

We have outlined and developed the formalism for the implementation of complex programmable photonic circuits taking as basic building blocks a special family of 2x2 reversible gates (known as rotation gates). By illustrating how these gates isomorphically correspond to well known photonic components we have then shown how these can be concatenated in two compact forms to implement tunable arbitrary 2x2 unitary transformers. These unitaries can be, in turn, assembled into two-dimensional configurations to feature field programmable gate arrays.

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